

Proceedings of the 3rd International Circular Packaging Conference

3 CIRCULAR
PACKAGING
CONFERENCE

Ljubljana and online
19th and 20th October 2023

PROCEEDINGS OF THE 3RD INTERNATIONAL CIRCULAR PACKAGING CONFERENCE

3RD CPC 2023

The Proceedings contain peer reviewed scientific and professional papers.

Publishers

Pulp and Paper Institute, Bogišičeva 8, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia
Faculty of Polymer Technology, Ozare 19, Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

For the publishers

David Ravnjak, PhD
Blaž Nardin, PhD

Editors

Urška Kavčič, PhD
Gregor Lavrič, PhD

Layout and design

Urška Kavčič, PhD
Gregor Lavrič, PhD

Place and date

Ljubljana, 2023

Kataložni zapis o publikaciji (CIP) pripravili v Narodni in univerzitetni knjižnici v Ljubljani

COBISS.SI-ID 168715779

ISBN 978-961-90424-9-6 (Inštitut za celulozo in papir, PDF)

***PROCEEDINGS OF THE 3RD INTERNATIONAL
CIRCULAR PACKAGING CONFERENCE***

Ljubljana and online, 19th and 20th October 2023

ORGANIZED BY

Pulp and Paper Institute, Ljubljana, Slovenia

Faculty of Polymer Technology, Slovenj Gradec, Slovenia

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Stefan Laske, PhD, Greiner Packaging (AT)

DI Herfried Lammer, Kompetenzzentrum Holz (AT)

Prof. Dragoljub Novaković, PhD, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad (RS)

Prof. Branka Lozo, PhD, Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb (HR)

Prof. Gregor Radonjič, PhD, Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Maribor (SI)

Prof. Arif Özcan, PhD, Marmara University, Instabul (TR)

Prof. Branka Pilić, PhD, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad (RS)

Milica Balaban, PhD, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka (BA)

Laszlo Koltai, PhD, Faculty of Light Industry and Environmental Engineering, Obudai University (HU)

Prof. Aleksandra Lobnik, PhD, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, University of Maribor (SI)

Prof. Urška Vrabič Brodnjak, PhD, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, University of Ljubljana (SI)

Barbara Prinčič, Academy of Fine Arts and Design, University of Ljubljana (SI)

Prof. Miroslav Huskić, PhD, Faculty of Polymer technology, Slovenj Gradec (SI)

Prof. Irena Pulko, PhD, Faculty of Polymer technology, Slovenj Gradec (SI)

Blaž Nardin, PhD, Faculty of Polymer technology, Slovenj Gradec (SI)

David Ravnjak, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Urška Kavčič, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Igor Karlovits, PhD, Danfoss Power Solutions (SI)

REVIEWING COMMITTEE

Peter Böröcz, PhD, Széchenyi István University (HU)

Ana Oberlintner, PhD, National Institute of Chemistry (SI)

Blanka Ravnjak, PhD, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Ljubljana (SI)

Tomislav Cigula, PhD, Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb (HR)

Sanja Mahović Poljaček, PhD, Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb (HR)

Sonja Jamnicki, PhD, Faculty of Graphic Arts, University of Zagreb (HR)

Branka Pilić, PhD, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad (RS)

Ivan Ristić, PhD, Faculty of Technology, University of Novi Sad (RS)

Milica Balaban, PhD, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Mathematics, University of Banja Luka (BA)

Urška Vrabič Brodnjak, PhD, Faculty of Natural Sciences and Engineering, University of Ljubljana (SI)

Sandra Dediđer, PhD, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad (RS)

Gorazd Golob, PhD, IARIGAI (SI)

David Ravnjak, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Urška Kavčič, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Igor Karlovits, PhD, Danfoss Power Solutions (SI)

Tea Kapun, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Gregor Lavrič, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

Mija Sežun, PhD, Pulp and Paper Institute (SI)

ORGANIZED BY

GENERAL SPONSOR

GOLDEN SPONSORS

SPONSOR

FOREWORD

Dear Readers,

The first time we organized the conference we had luck, the second time it became a pattern and the third time, it became a habit. All people involved already are aligned to organize this conference every second year, and even if it becomes a habit, we still feel lucky to be able to talk and collaborate with amazing companies, authors, researchers, speakers, and stakeholders. In this mutual journey, we must all align and collaborate towards eliminating littering and damage to Nature either through raw material depletion or by the intended or unintended release of toxic components in soil, water, or air.

The only constant on Planet Earth is change. The climate is changing, the world as we know it has changed more dramatically in the last few years and months and the policy on packaging waste at least in Europe is expected to be changed. This will also have a great impact on the packaging landscape, from materials producers, and production companies to the recycling stakeholders which need to fulfil the demand for recycled content ratio. But we must not forget that the circularity hierarchy starts with reducing and rethinking the processes and the whole supply chain and product lifecycle. So we must all also change, to see the big picture, not the small conveniences.

This conference is also changing as new young forces will carry the torch and organization of this conference further to expand this community and enlarge the circle of collaborators. The new generations will hopefully make their habit of coming to Slovenia every second year to the Circular Packaging Conference.

In the name of all involved in the organization, I want to thank the sponsors, authors, companies, and reviewers for their efforts and dedicated work to make this event happen again. I want to personally thank the organizing team and especially Urška and Gregor who put great effort into organizing and elevating this conference to new heights through all these changes.

In Ljubljana, 19th October 2023

PhD Igor Karlovits

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ENZYMES AS INNOVATION FOR BIOBASED PACKAGING AT THE FOOD VALUE CHAIN..9	
VALUE CHAIN GENERATOR	17
EVALUATION AND ENHANCEMENT OF RECYCLABILITY FOR COATED PACKAGING PAPERS	27
INFLUENCE OF RAW MATERIAL CHARACTERISTICS ON THE PULP MOLDING PROCESS	37
MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF SHRINK PE FILMS.....	44
CHALLENGES IN DESIGNING SUSTAINABLE PAPER PACKAGING FROM INVASIVE PLANTS	53
CHALLENGES IN THE REPLACEMENT OF EPS PACKAGING WITH THE BIOBASED ONE IN A LARGE SCALE PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENT	63
A PRELIMINARY ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF ALTERNATIVE LIGNOCELLULOSIC FIBRES IN INDUSTRIAL PACKAGING	73
STRATEGIES FOR THE MANAGEMENT OF INVASIVE PLANT SPECIES	78
DEVELOPMENT OF MOULDED PULP PROTECTIVE PACKAGING FROM ALTERNATIVE FIBERS	91
SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING INNOVATIONS IN THE FASHION SECTOR: PROGRESS, CHALLENGES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS	103
SUSTAINABLE FOOD PACKAGING: EMPOWERING CONSUMERS WITH COLOR-CODED SUGAR CONTENT AWARENESS	111
REVIEW OF GLOBAL PRODUCTION AND MARKET ANALYSIS OF BIOPLASTIC PACKAGING	119
DESIGN FOR RECYCLING GUIDELINES OF PAPER-BASED PACKAGING – A REVIEW FOR PACKAGING DESIGNERS	128
COMPARISON OF FILM PRESS AND SPRAY APPLICATION OF BIOPOLYMER BARRIER COATINGS ON PAPER	140
MOISTURE AND OIL RETENTION IN COATED PAPERS FOR FLEXIBLE FOOD PACKAGING: A STUDY ON BARRIER PROPERTIES AND SURFACE CHARACTERISTICS	143
BIODEGRADABLE FILMS BASED ON PHBV/PBAT BLENDS AND HEMP FIBERS FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS.....	153

INVESTIGATING THE AGING STABILITY AND THERMAL PROPERTIES OF CHITOSAN-COATED PAPER FOR SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING APPLICATIONS.....	156
SLOT-DIE COATING OF CELLULOSE NANOCRYSTALS AND CHITOSAN FOR AN IMPROVED BARRIER PROPERTIES OF PAPER	164
THE INFLUENCE OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BIOPOLYMER MATERIALS BASED ON CAMELINA OIL CAKE	171
POLYLACTIC ACID (PLA) AND SODIUM ALGINATE FILM PRODUCTION AND USAGE IN ACTIVE PACKAGING FOR TOMATO PRESERVATION.....	180
AN ECO-FRIENDLY SMART PACKAGING FILM WITH CARREGENAAN AND ANTHOCYANIN	190
MODIFICATION OF PLA-BASED BIO-NANOCOMPOSITE WITH NCC	199
MECHANICAL RECYCLING OF PRE-CONSUMER POLYETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE (PET) WASTE	209
BIO-SUSHY PFAS FREE SOLUTION WITH FOCUS ON THERMOPLASTIC BASED POWDERS FOR FOOD PACKAGING APPLICATIONS.....	218
SN-CATALYSIS AS AN EFFICIENT DEPOLYMERIZATION STEP OF POLY(LACTIDE) TO LACTIDE	219
DEPOLYMERISATION OF POST-CONSUMER PET BOTTLES WITH AMINOLYSIS IN THE PRESENCE OF ORGANOCATALYST	232
WATER DISPERSABILITY OF PAPERS– BALANCING MATERIAL STRENGTH AND DISPERSIBILITY	238
FOOD PACKAGING PAPERS BASED ON BIOPOLYMERS POLYELECTROLYTE COMPLEXES	240
HEMP AND RICE STRAW VALORIZATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SUSTAINABLE ANTIOXIDANT-CELLULOSIC BASED CRYOGELS AND AEROGELS	242
INK PRODUCTION WITH NATURAL SINOP CLAY PIGMENT AND EXAMINATION PRINTABILITY PROPERTIES OF ECO-FRIENDLY INK.....	245
DIGITAL PRINTING IN THE PACKAGING INDUSTRY.....	253
APPLICATION OF INK WITH PUFF EFFECT FOR IMPROVEMENT OF ERGONOMIC PROPERTIES OF PACKAGING	268
THE POSSIBILITY OF PRINTING ON BIOPOLYMER PACKAGING MATERIALS	278

REVIEW OF GLOBAL PRODUCTION AND MARKET ANALYSIS OF BIOPLASTIC PACKAGING

Mirica Karlovits, Uroš Novak, Blaž Likozar

National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia

Professional paper

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10007646

mirica.karlovits@ki.si

Abstract: *Packaging generates environmental impact throughout its life cycle, so developing new packaging solutions is necessary to minimize environmental pollution. The rising environmental concerns owing to the increasing amount of plastic packaging waste across the globe, especially across developing economies, are driving the demand for bioplastic packaging. The bioplastic packaging market is predicted to increase significantly as a result of the strict regulatory environment, the worldwide environmental crisis, and other factors. Accordingly, the present review study deals with market size analysis, market share, growth factors as well as future forecasts in bioplastics packaging.*

Keywords: bioplastics, packaging, sustainability, environment, market analysis, CAGR

1 INTRODUCTION

Packaging development has become a great challenging task and of enormous responsibility for the manufacturers and the professionals involved (Bucci et al., 2007). Businesses are under pressure not only from consumers but also from governments to use eco-friendly packaging for their products (Nguyen et al., 2020).

More than 70% of the world's largest companies have committed themselves to reducing plastics pollution. It was recently concluded that the implementation of “circular innovations” for packaging on a global level is still low (Lisiecki et al., 2023). As a result of plastic waste, Earth’s ocean and freshwater biodiversity and ecosystems are being negatively affected. The magnitude of plastic pollution carried to sea has significantly multiplied over the past several decades. Oftentimes, wildlife is injured due to entanglement or ingestion of the plastics

found in the environment. For Procellariiformes such as the albatrosses, shearwaters, or petrels, the appearance of eroded plastic pieces are similar to many types of food they consume. Microplastics resemble phytoplankton which are eaten by fish and cetaceans. Ingested plastic debris has been found to reduce stomach capacity, hinder growth, cause internal injuries, and create intestinal blockage. Plastic entanglement with fishing nets or other ring-shaped materials can result in strangulation, reduction of feeding efficiency, and in some cases drowning (Sigler, 2014).

Growing concern about human health and environmental aspects has driven the focus more towards eco-friendly, biodegradable, and sustainable packaging materials (Surendren et al., 2022). In that sense, seeking new sustainable materials to replace petroleum-based plastics has led to the development of a new group of materials, termed bioplastics. The term bioplastic is mostly used to define plastics that can be either bio-based, biodegradable, or both (Shlush et al., 2022). Bioplastics are not just one single material. They comprise of whole family of materials with different properties and applications. The term ‘biobased’ means that the material or product is (partly) derived from biomass (plants). Biomass used for bioplastics stems from e.g. corn, sugarcane, or cellulose.

Figure 1. Material coordinate system for bioplastics (Bioplastics, 2023).

With respect to environmental impact, as opposed to their fossil- and petrol-based counterparts, polymers from natural sources significantly reduce the final product carbon footprint, the industry dependency on scarce resources and

leads to lower emission of greenhouse gas and other toxic compounds to the atmosphere (Shlush et al., 2022).

Bioplastics are gaining significant traction and they are suitable for a broad range of end-of-life options, including packaging. The expanding trend of sustainability in many packaging elements is driving the bioplastic packaging market. Due to the widespread use of packaging products and the rising aversion to plastic packaging with a high risk of contamination, the food and beverage sectors are recognized as the top consumers of bioplastic packaging. (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2023).

This is owing to high consumer awareness, supportive government initiatives, and continuous innovation in biodegradable packaging in the market. Stringent regulations over conventional plastic use in food, beverage, and medical packaging has led to increasing adoption of these (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2022).

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

Market analysis is a comprehensive study of a specific market within an industry, including an examination of its various components, such as market size and trends, target audience, profitability and growth rate (Market Analysis, 2023). The aim of this review paper was to evaluate and understand bioplastic packaging market. The analysis is based on open-access market reports from 2022 to 2030.

2. 1 Global production of bioplastics

Currently, bioplastics still represent < 1% of the more than 390 million tonnes of plastic produced annually. After stagnating in 2020, mainly due to Covid-19, the overall global plastic production has been increasing again since 2021. This development is driven by rising demand combined with the emergence of more sophisticated applications and products.

According to the latest market data, the global bioplastics production capacities are set to increase from around 2.2 million tonnes in 2022 to approximately 6.3 million tonnes in 2027. Figure 2 shows the global production capacities of bioplastics in tones in period 2021-2027.

Figure 2. Global production capacities of bioplastics, 2022-2027.

Bioplastics are used in an increasing number of markets, from packaging, catering products, consumer electronics, automotive, agriculture/horticulture, and toys to textiles and several other segments. Packaging remains the largest market segment for bioplastics with 48% (almost 1.1 million tonnes) of the total bioplastics market in 2022. However, the portfolio of applications continues to diversify. Segments, such as automotives & transport or building & construction, remain on the rise with growing capacities of functional polymers.

Figure 3. Global production capacities of bioplastics 2022 (by market segment).

With a view to regional capacity development, Asia further strengthened its position as major production hub with more than 41% of bioplastics currently being produced in the region. Presently, just over a quarter of the production capacity is still located in Europe. However, Europe's share and that of other

world regions will significantly decrease within the next five years. In contrast, Asia's production capacities are predicted to increase to almost 63% by 2027.

Figure 4. Global production capacities of bioplastics 2027 (by region) (Bioplastics, 2023, Ferreira et al., 2023).

2. 2 Market size and growth rate

Market size refers to the total sales generated in a specific period and provides insight into the current sales volume and future sales projections. Market size is influenced by market demand, and businesses can gather information on market size through surveys, government data, trade publications, and financial reports (Market Analysis, 2023).

The changed post Covid-19 business landscape, the global market for plastic packaging estimated at USD 702.4 Billion in the year 2022, is projected to reach a revised size of USD 944.3 Billion by 2030, growing at a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 3.8% over the analysis period 2022-2030.

Figure 5. Global market for plastic packaging.

However, the increasing need for sustainable materials has developed a dynamic rise in bioplastics production in the upcoming years. The global bioplastic packaging market size was exhibited at USD 15.6 Billion in 2022 and is projected to attain around USD 58 Billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR of 14.02% during the forecast period 2023 to 2032.

Figure 6. Global market for bioplastic packaging.

2. 3 Market share

The expanding trend of sustainability in many packaging elements is driving the bioplastic packaging market. Due to the widespread use of packaging products and the rising aversion to plastic packaging with a high risk of contamination, the food and beverage sectors are recognized as the top consumers of bioplastic packaging.

Regarding application, the food and beverage sector held a significant market share in 2022, accounting for 59% (Figure 7). The market is being driven by the increased prominence of quick-service restaurants and the demand for packaged food. The industry for flexible packaging will likely rise during the forecast period because manufacturers are expanding their production capacity in response to the rising demand for packaged goods.

Figure 7. Bioplastic packaging market share, by application in 2022.

In terms of revenue, the bioplastics packaging market in Europe held the highest share 34% in 2022. Due to strict environmental legislation and rising consumer concern for the environment, the region will likely experience significant growth in the years to come.

Figure 8. Bioplastic packaging market share, by region, 2022 (%).

Europe follows North America and the Asia Pacific region in terms of projected market expansion. The bioplastics packaging material market will likely grow significantly in Japan, the U.S., China, and Germany.

Government initiatives will also increase bioplastic demand over the evaluation period, such as the decision of the E.U. to lessen the widespread use of single-use plastic products. The European Parliament decided to ban single-use plastic products like cutlery and straws in 2019 as part of a comprehensive rule against plastic rubbish that damages beaches and pollutes waterways. In July 2021, a ban on single-use plastics was anticipated to go into effect (Bioplastics Packaging Market, 2023).

3 CONCLUSIONS

It is understood that one of the major benefits of going bioplastics packaging is the preservation and well-being of the environment we live in. Awareness and concerns about environmental issues are growing among consumers. Recent studies demonstrate that despite the economic crisis, consumers in developed countries affirm their wish for eco-friendly packaging more than ever before. Bioplastics are expected to displace conventional plastic in many industries due to the numerous benefits, especially in food and beverage packaging industry.

Acknowledgement: *The authors would like to acknowledge the financial support of Horizon Europe projects REMEDIES (GA 101093964) and UPSTREAM (GA 10112877).*

Abbreviations: PE - Polyethylene; PEF – Polyethylene Furanoate; PET - Polyethylene terephthalate; PTT - poly trimethylene terephthalate; PLA - Poly Lactic Acid; PHA – Polyhydroxyalkanoate; PBS - Polybutylene succinate; PP - Polypropylene; PMMA - Polymethylmethacrylate Acrylic; PVC - Polyvinyl chloride; PBAT - Polybutylene adipate terephthalate; PCL – Polycaprolactone.

4 REFERENCES

Bioplastics (2023) European Bioplastics e.V. Available at: <https://www.european-bioplastics.org/bioplastics/> (Accessed: 02 August 2023).

Bioplastic Packaging Market, by product type by end-use, by region - size, share, outlook, and opportunity analysis, 2022 – 2030 (2022). Available at: <https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/5714397/bioplastic-packaging-market-by-product-type-by#tag-pos-1> (Accessed: 02 August 2023).

Bioplastic Packaging Market (By Material: Biodegradable, Non-biodegradable; By Type: Rigid, Flexible; By Application: Consumer Goods, Food & Beverages,

Pharmaceuticals, Cosmetic & Personal Care, others) - Global Industry Analysis, Size, Share, Growth, Trends, Regional Outlook, and Forecast 2023-2032 (2023) Precedence Research. Available at: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/bioplastic-packaging-market> (Accessed: 02 August 2023).

Bucci, D.Z. and Forcellini, F.A. (2007) Sustainable Packaging Design model. *Complex Systems Concurrent Engineering*, pp. 363–370.

Lisiecki M., Damgaard A., Ragaert K. and Astrup T.F (2023) Circular economy initiatives are no guarantee for increased plastic circularity: A framework for the systematic comparison of initiatives. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*. 197, p. 107072.

Market Analysis - what is it, examples, importance, methods (2023). Available at: <https://www.wallstreetmojo.com/market-analysis/> (Accessed: 02 August 2023).

Ferreira D.C.M., Natalina dos Santos P., Santos F.H., Molina G., Pelissari F.M. (2023) Sustainability approaches for agro waste solution: Biodegradable packaging and microbial polysaccharides bio-production. *Science of the Total Environment*. 886, p. 163922.

Nguyen A.T., Parker L., Brennan L., Lockrey S. (2020) A consumer definition of eco-friendly packaging. *Journal of Cleaner Production*. 252, p. 119792.

Plastic packaging (2023): Global strategic business report, Research and Markets - Market Research Reports. Available at: https://www.researchandmarkets.com/reports/362133/plastic_packaging_global_strategic_business#cat-pos-3 (Accessed: 02 August 2023).

Shlush, E. and Davidovich-Pinhas, M. (2022) Bioplastics for Food Packaging, *Trends in Food Science & Technology*. 125, pp. 66–80.

Sigler M. (2014) The Effects of Plastic Pollution on Aquatic Wildlife: Current Situations and Future Solutions. *Water Air Soil Pollut*. 225:2184.

Surendren A., Mohantly A., Liu Q., Misra M. (2022) A review of biodegradable thermoplastic starches, their blends and composites: recent developments

and opportunities for single-use plastic packaging alternatives. *Green Chemistry*, 24, pp. 8606-8636.